

DICTIONARIES OF PEDAGOGICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK AND THEIR FUNCTIONS.

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Annotation: *Dictionary - 1) a set of words, vocabulary, existing in a particular language, its regional or social dialect, found in the works of this or that writer; 2) a book in which words (or morphemes, phrases, phrases, etc.) are placed in a certain order (alphabetical, thematic), descriptive units, their origin, meanings, spelling, pronunciation, stylistic affiliation, translation into other languages. Dictionaries play an important role in the field of spiritual culture, reflecting the knowledge acquired by a society over a period of time. Pedagogical dictionaries - classify terms in the field of pedagogy.*

Key words: *phrases, expressions, pedagogical terms, pedagogical lexicographic sources, international pedagogical terminology, education, monolingual pedagogical dictionary, multilingual / bilingual pedagogical dictionary, monolingual encyclopedic dictionary.*

Problems in the field of pedagogical terminology can not be solved without understanding the essence of the categories "term", "concept", "system" terms or "terminology". it is defined by a word or phrase. A phrase is a term (Lat. terminus - "boundary", "boundary"). In fact, pedagogical terminology and concepts are crucial for the development of pedagogy. deals with the output.

Pedagogical lexicographic sources and consideration of the following issues:

- Types of pedagogical lexicographic sources; their elements and parameters;
- The basics of building pedagogical lexicographic sources and the possibility of using computer technology;
- Development and formation of algorithms for pedagogical creation of lexicographic sources; planning and organization of lexical and graphic activities;
- Selection of terms and formation of pedagogical lexicographic source;
- variants of interpretation of different terminological units, different types of dictionaries;
- Typology of pedagogical lexicographic sources;
- Consistency and consistency in international pedagogical terminology;

It should be noted that the function of pedagogical terms in dictionaries is as follows:

- Definition of pedagogical terms and connections between them;

- Analysis and modeling of the system of pedagogical terms based on the identified concepts and their relationship;
- Conditions for creating an image of the system of terms through diagrams

- definition of terms, definition of symbols (mainly terms) one or more languages for each pedagogical concept;

- Identification and presentation of terminological information in print and electronic forms (terminography) (M. Pottsi, 1999)

Use of new communication and computer technologies in the field of definition of developing pedagogical terminology in the process of professional pedagogical communication;

The transmission and exchange of knowledge between people of different cultures and speakers of different languages is aimed at studying the following aspects:

- knowledge of pedagogical terminology and pedagogical science (pedagogical concept) and "pedagogical term", conceptual analysis of pedagogical terminology, structural principles of pedagogical terminology, conceptual models of terminology, terminological approach to presentation, combination of scientific and pedagogical ontological and terminological approaches creation of information systems, etc.);

- Management of information resources of pedagogical knowledge (definition of contextual information, automatic procedures for obtaining pedagogical terminology). Pedagogical terminology, terminological bases, data, their use in conceptual indexing; relationship between text documents in the field of pedagogy and education and international pedagogical terminology, thesauruses for automatic indexing: structure, development and use, terminology logical means, creation of machine banks of pedagogical terminology, etc.);

- Pedagogical terminology in terms of the process of professional intercultural pedagogical communication and knowledge transfer;

- International pedagogical terminology: problems of localization and internationalization in contrast to global and regional;

- pedagogical terminology in terms of development global computer networks;

- Information society of pedagogical terminology in multimedia (multilingual terminological bases in the field of pedagogy and education, their creation and activity; exchange of terminological data and the role of terminological infrastructure in multimedia age);

- Approaches to the presentation of scientific and pedagogical knowledge; problems of conceptual navigation in multimedia multicultural information research and educational spaces;

From the point of view of information, all information about the terms in the lexicographic pedagogical source is considered as follows:

- scientific-pedagogical (information concept about scientific pedagogy);
- Linguistic (characterized by features such as etymological information, semantically close terms, history of origin. Term, history of use of the term, usage of the term, foreign equivalents, grammatical features of the term, use of examples, etc.);
- cultural (reflected in features such as context). Use in a particular pedagogical culture, regional data, etc.)

According to the accepted parameters, pedagogical lexicographic sources are structured as follows:

1. **Monolingual pedagogical dictionary** (short general dictionary of pedagogical terms or terminology, created in the field of pedagogy).

For example: 1) Glossary of US Educational Terminology (Assefa) Glossary of United States Educational Terminology Mariam Assefa, PresidentWorld Education Services, New York; 2) Educational Terminology. zur learn: line Homepage, Educational Terminology. betreut durch John Eccleston .; 3) Educational Terminology Alphabetical index of educational terms.ADMISSION CRITERIA; 4) Educational terminology Eurydice; 5) Glossary of United States Educational Terminology.

2. **Multilingual / bilingual pedagogical dictionary** (a brief general translation dictionary of pedagogical terms or terminological expressions, collection. Examples: 1) Finnish-English Educational Terminology Glossary - Finnish-English education Glossary of Terminology: Finnish-English Educational Terminology Glossary FAST-US-5 US Education Survey FAST 177 Area Studies Program, Department of Translation Studies; 2) Educational terminology; Hungary OSEAS EUROPE EDUCATIONAL TERMINOLOGY. HUNGARY. Types of institutions, ovoda (kindergarten), iskola (school), altalanos iskola (primary school, general school);

3. **Monolingual encyclopedic dictionary, reference dictionary (a scientific-pedagogical lexicographic source** containing a systematized set of knowledge on pedagogy, public education and related disciplines, arranged in alphabetical order; thematic (systematic) or alphabetical-thematic order;

briefly reveals the general theory of pedagogy, its history, specific disciplines, describes the system and state of education. For example: 1) V.V. 2-volume Russian pedagogical encyclopedia named after Davydov, M .: BRE, 1993. 2) DICTIONARY OF EDUCATION PLUS (Server) (includes a practical dictionary of terms in the field of pedagogical research, a bibliographic commentary for each defined term, as well as excerpts from articles describing the context in which the term is used) <http://macwe.umich.edu/plus/> (located at the University of Michigan).

4. Multilingual / bilingual encyclopedic dictionary, a dictionary (pedagogical lexicographic source, which includes a systematized set of knowledge on pedagogy, folklore and related disciplines, briefly discloses general information . Pedagogical theory, its history, individual disciplines, description of the education system and status in different countries). For example: 1. The Learner's English - Russian Dictionary of Education / English - 1998. 2. School English-Russian and Russian-English Dictionary, 2000

EDUCATION (as a pedagogical phenomenon) - the purposeful professional activity of the teacher, contributes to the maximum development of the child's personality, his entry into the context of modern culture, becoming a subject of his life, the formation of his motives and values. In dictionaries of comparable languages we can find as follows, we have interpreted it in connection with its types:

TARBIYA (pedagogik hodisa sifatida) - o'qituvchining maqsadli kasbiy faoliyati, bolaning shaxsiyatining maksimal rivojlanishiga, uning zamonaviy madaniyat kontekstiga kirishiga, o'z hayotining sub'ektiga aylanishiga, uning motivlari va qadriyatlarining shakllanishiga hissa qo'shadi. Pedagogika sohasidagi "Tarbiya" atamasi qiyoslanayotgan tillardagi lug'atlarda quyudagicha uchratishimiz mumkin, uning turlari bilan bog'lab talqin qildik: